

Peculiarities of Social Protection of the Population in a Pandemic Condition: Economic and Legal Analysis

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Abstract

To achieve this goal it was: analyzed the concept of social protection and identify its tools; identified key regulations that determine the features of social protection in a pandemic COVID-19, compared the means of social protection of the Member States of the European Union; formulated concrete and substantiated proposals for improving the level of social protection of the population in the context of the COVID–19 pandemic. The following methods were actively used for economic and legal analysis of social protection: comparative legal method in the study of social protection in Ukraine and other countries, in the process of which it was found that Ukraine has actively adopted the international experience of the Coronavirus Fund an integral part of the budget of Ukraine. In the article, the authors analyzed the existing and proposed new measures of social protection in a pandemic COVID-19. The results of the study can be used for further theoretical research and improvement of existing legislation.

Keywords: state aid, financial security, labor rights, vulnerable categories of the population, pandemic fight fund.

1. Introduction

At the end of 2019, humanity was held hostage by the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19), which was rapidly gaining momentum. The first cases of acute respiratory disease COVID-19 caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 were recorded in the Chinese city of Wuhan. In 2020,

almost a year after the spread of the virus, the World Health Organization (WHO) provided statistics confirming a positive diagnosis of COVID-19 in more than 76 million people, with the number of deaths exceeding 1 million 700 thousand victims of coronavirus. The current global systemic crisis has a threefold burden - it is both epidemiological and geopolitical, as well as economic and social (Treshchov, 2020). As of mid-2021, most countries affected by the disease have become exporters or importers of the vaccine to their residents. However, despite the fairly rapid rate of vaccination of the population – still the disease has not receded.

The pandemic caused by this virus has already caused millions in human casualties around the world, and has caused significant restrictions on the socio-cultural life of the population, including global trends in the world economy (Pidlipna, 2015). To date, it is extremely difficult to predict the final human casualties and economic losses suffered by states in the long or short term. At the same time, it is necessary that individual economic development forecasts and measures selected by the governments of the world's leading countries be able to have the negative consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. And this, in turn, will allow for the formation of a realistic vision of the possible course of economic processes that will have a direct impact on the level of social and economic life of the population.

Of course, the life and health of the population is the most important priority, which is guaranteed by the Constitution of Ukraine, but the economic losses from this disease, which undermined the stability in the economic situation of our state, are too high (Bobrova & Lomonosova, 2020). In 2020 and 2021, employers and trade unions face major challenges related to the coronavirus pandemic and quarantine, as well as the economic crisis, new models and approaches to working time management, and increasing discrimination and stigma in the workplace. Therefore, in such difficult conditions, the need for state support in the form of social protection of the population in order to return their residents to normal and comfortable living becomes relevant.

Social protection of the population is a key mechanism of support from the state for socially vulnerable categories of the population, which is essentially an inactive group of citizens of Ukraine (Strizhkova, 2020). However, it is precisely in the context of the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic that the economically active population, without reference to their type of economic activity or turnover, needs special financial and preferential support from the state as never before (Wagner, 2020).

The following methods were actively used for economic and legal analysis of social protection: comparative legal method in the study of social protection in Ukraine and other countries, in the process of which it was found that Ukraine has actively adopted the international experience of the Coronavirus Fund. an integral part of the budget of Ukraine; The statistical method was used in the analysis of the main indicators presented in the process of analysis of social protection of the population in the Member States of the European Union and Ukraine; The logical-semantic method allowed to determine the conceptual apparatus used in the study, and it was with its help that the concept of social protection of the population, the Coronavirus Control Fund, was defined. General scientific methods – analysis and synthesis – were also used.

Analysis of recent research and publications proves a certain interest of both legal professionals and modern economists in the relevance of social protection in Covid-19, among which are: O. Artemenko, L. Krupnova, L. Kurylo, S. Kovalova and L. Kniazka (2020), I.I. Smirnova, O.Yu. Likhoshva, N.V. Cancer and L.A. Goriev (2020), N. Borodchuk and L. Cherenko (2020), A. Bobrova and L. Lomonosova (2020), I.M. Wagner (2020), M.M. Treshchov (2020) and others.

In particular, M.M. Treshchov (2020) proposed that domestic borrowings in the state budget should increase by UAH 146.5 billion against the background of an increase in their repayment during 2020 by UAH 54.4 billion. That is, nominally it is planned to increase the

volume of domestic borrowing by UAH 92.1 billion, which in the current situation of rapid sale by non-residents of IGLBs (which only in March 2020 sold bonds worth UAH 8 billion) against the background of rising US dollar and euro, is possible only with an additional issue of hryvnia by the National Bank, which in the conditions of stagnation of the Ukrainian economy will accelerate inflation. He summed up the inferiority of the newly created stabilization fund as a tool for budgetary regulation of the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in Ukraine and the world.

I.M. Wagner (2020) studied the impact of COVID-19 on the economic development of small and medium-sized businesses in Ukraine and notes that “the main consequences of COVID-19 for the world economy are already: falling stock indices; significant reduction of oil prices and slowdown of the metal market; reduction of production; significant reduction in revenues of airlines and maritime transport, shopping and entertainment centers, the tourism industry; reduction of household income; growth of profits of the pharmaceutical industry and the world industry of game, educational and other online applications; growing investor demand for less risky assets. For Ukraine's economy, the crisis caused by the spread of COVID-19 is particularly dangerous and could significantly shake the country's financial and economic situation: there will be a drop in official employment and real GDP, the corporate sector will suffer significant losses, the chances of successful Eurobond placement will decrease. depreciation of the national currency”.

2. Material and Financial Support as an Economic Component of State Development During a Pandemic

In the context of any social cataclysm (whether man-made or biological danger), first of all, it is worth paying attention to the protection of human rights. Because it is on the path of Ukraine's integration into full membership in the European Union (hereinafter - the EU) that the key task is to ensure the realization of the rights and freedoms of man and citizen defined by the Constitution of Ukraine. Improving domestic legislation on social protection and bringing it in line with global legal standards of human rights - which in turn is one of the most important tasks of a democratic and legal state.

Therefore, one of the key tasks of any modern, democratic, socially oriented state is to create all the necessary organizational and legal conditions for social protection. This provision is enshrined in Article 46 of the Constitution of Ukraine, according to which “citizens have the right to social protection, which includes the right to provide them in case of full, partial or temporary disability, loss of breadwinner, unemployment due to circumstances beyond their control, and also in old age and in other cases provided by law. This right is guaranteed by the obligatory state social insurance at the expense of insurance premiums of citizens, enterprises, institutions and organizations, as well as budgetary and other sources of social security; creation of a network of state, communal, private institutions for the care of the disabled (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996). No less important is the mention of doctrinal definitions, because quite often scholars interpret and explain in more detail the definitions defined by the legislator.

According to L.I. Didkivska and L.S. Golovko (2009), social protection of the population is “state support of certain categories of the population that may be negatively affected by market processes, ensuring an adequate standard of living by providing legal, financial and material assistance. to individual citizens (the most vulnerable segments of the population), as well as the creation of social guarantees for the economically active part of the population, ensuring acceptable living and working conditions for citizens, including through the establishment of social standards”.

According to R.P. Pidlipna (2015), social protection is not only an integral part of the social policy of any state, but it is an indisputable requirement for the civilizational existence at a sufficiently high level of every citizen without exception. After all, a person as the main

guarantor of the existence of society should feel care and human attitude, as a certain guarantee of the existence of the state and law. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to social protection and social groups that are directly dependent on the state, while the state provides historical recognition of the past, as well as stability in the modern functioning and happy existence of citizens in the future, which is essentially the main basis for democratic legal welfare state.

L.B. Barannyk (2017) notes that the task of most social protection systems is to maintain the stability of people's incomes, provide equal access to health care and necessary social services. As an organized system, it exists in many countries around the world. In economically developed countries, social protection is an important part of the national economy, the cost of which is now more than a quarter of GDP. The EU countries have the most developed social protection systems. It was in them that the first social programs appeared and developed. As the experience of these countries shows, "the existence of a well-thought-out social protection system that covers all citizens not only improves their well-being, expands and strengthens the country's labor resources, but also contributes to economic growth and stabilization of political and social situation in the country. Thus, social protection has a positive effect on society, contributes to social harmony and ensures a common sense of social security among its members".

Based on the above, we can say that in economically developed countries, the cost of social protection, not only in terms of coronavirus disease, but in general - is a priority for the use of budget funds. According to a survey conducted in August by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (hereinafter - the EBRD) together with the research center Info Institute, the coronary crisis has worsened the financial condition of 68% of Ukrainian households. Almost a third (26%) even started saving on food. UNICEF estimates that more than 6 million Ukrainian women (1.4 million of them children) may be below the poverty line due to the socio-economic crisis caused by COVID-19. According to the Ministry of Social Policy, at the end of March, an additional 20,000 people were identified who needed state assistance (Borodchuk & Cherenko, 2020). The need to find out the basic means for the implementation of social protection will also be important in the study. According to I.I. Smirnova (Smirnova et al., 2020), social protection of the population in Ukraine can be realized with the help of:

- material support of the economically active population (through social insurance);
- pension provision of the population;
- providing social assistance to the most vulnerable categories;
- providing financial assistance to families with children;
- issuance of compensations, indexations, as well as special benefits for the population;
- organization of social services, etc. Thus, social protection is provided through social security and social assistance.

Citizens of Ukraine faced a problem permanent quarantine restrictions, which has an impact on financial and material security and which causes massive job cuts, reduction or loss of wages, etc. A.L. Klymenko (2017) notes that financial support of social protection of citizens has a multi-channel structure, which consists of state and local budgets, state and non-state social funds, economic entities of various forms of ownership and charitable (charitable) funds and is carried out by redistributing the value of gross domestic product on the basis of social solidarity, which provides for mutual assistance of all participants in the social protection system. Such mutual assistance is realized in the form of redistribution of funds between different socio-economic and socio-demographic groups of the population.

O.V. Artemenko (Artemenko et al., 2020) notes that in Ukraine budget financing of social protection and social security of the population today is carried out in accordance with the provisions of Art. 87-91 of the Budget Code of Ukraine (2010) at the expense of the state and

local budgets and are directed on financing: social protection in case of incapacity for work; social protection of pensioners; social protection of war and labor veterans; social protection of families, children and youth; social protection of the unemployed; assistance in resolving the housing issue; social protection of other categories of the population; basic and applied research and development in the field of social protection; other activities in the field of social protection. Along with social protection, it is also worth remembering about social services, as they are usually financed from budgets of different levels, and funding schemes differ significantly depending on which budget manager belongs to which social institution (Artemenko et al., 2020).

In order to properly and rationally dispose of funds needed to overcome coronavirus disease, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On approval of the Procedure for the use of the fund to combat acute respiratory disease COVID-19 caused by coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 and its consequences" The main mechanism for using the COVID-19 Acute Respiratory Disease Fund caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus and its consequences was established, which is created within the state budget for the period of quarantine established by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine to prevent the spread of Ukraine of the specified disease, and within 30 days from the date of cancellation of quarantine (The Cabinet of Ministers, 2020d).

Thus, at the expense of the state budget in 2020 in Ukraine the Fund of struggle against a coronavirus infection and its consequences for the period of action of quarantine and within 30 days from the date of cancellation of this quarantine functions. At the beginning of its establishment, the COVID-19 Anti-Crisis Fund amounted to about UAH 65 billion, which was distributed through sequestration and changes to the state budget. In particular, it concerned the reduction of expenditures on culture, the reduction of the budget of the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine, the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Agriculture of Ukraine, as well as the growth of the state budget deficit. However, by the end of 2020, the final amount of the Fund to Combat COVID-19 amounted to 80.9 billion hryvnias.

M.M. Treshtov (2020) notes that the use of the fund includes funding for measures to prevent the occurrence and spread, localization and elimination of outbreaks, epidemics and pandemics, including the purchase of goods, works and services necessary for such activities, including the purchase of medical services under the state guarantee program medical care. In addition, the following most significant expenditures were included in the anti-crisis areas of redistribution of state budget funds:

- UAH 15.8 billion for the implementation of the program of state guarantees of medical care (additional payments to the salaries of medical and other workers who are directly employed in the elimination of the disease, and who provide the livelihood of the population, for the period of quarantine);

- UAH 10 billion for additional payments to the elderly;

- 0.6 billion UAH to provide assistance from the Fund of Compulsory State Social Insurance of Ukraine in the event of unemployment.

As we can see, the Fund to Combat COVID-19 concerns, inter alia, social benefits to the population, which found itself in a difficult financial situation as a result of the pandemic. However, if we compare the figures of the member states of the European Union, the amounts allocated to Ukraine are simply meager (Fig. 1). For example, the Italian government has approved several packages of economic measures totaling € 750 billion to support business as part of strengthening pandemic rules and government guarantees for loans and investments. According to the approved decisions, 340 billion euros are allocated in the form of public loans, 400 billion euros - to support liquidity of enterprises of all categories and forms of ownership, including: 200 billion euros - for the domestic market and the same - for export (Consiglio dei Ministri, 2020).

The Government of the Federal Republic of Germany (hereinafter - Germany) went further and adopted a package of measures aimed at supporting businesses and citizens during the pandemic of more than 750 billion euros. In particular, € 600 billion is earmarked for the creation of a loan fund and the nationalization of large enterprises that will be particularly hard hit by the crisis. To help small businesses and citizens, 156 billion euros will be allocated, which includes, among other things, a reduction in tax revenues by 33.5 billion euros through tax holidays. € 50 billion of this money will be allocated to support self-employed people as well as small businesses. Among the measures of social support of the population: tenants must be protected from loss of housing, even in the presence of rent arrears (Mind, 2020).

EU finance ministers have agreed on a € 540 billion economic package to support the EU economy, including: € 100 billion in wage subsidies, provided that companies cut workers' working hours without cutting jobs; EUR 200 billion - expansion of corporate lending programs; 240 billion euros - financing of "cheap" loans under the European Stability Mechanism (Strupczewski & Baczynska, 2020). On the example of the distribution of budget funds in Germany, aimed at overcoming the complex economic consequences of coronavirus disease, we can emphasize the priority and importance for the state economy, namely the support of large/small and medium-sized businesses.

The government of the neighboring state – the Republic of Poland has created a project called "Economic and social anti-crisis shield for the safety of entrepreneurs and workers in connection with the pandemic of the SARS-Cov-2 virus." It will cost about \$ 52 billion. These steps include protecting workers from job losses, health care, financial system security, business support, and public investment. For example, the state will cover 40% of the salaries of company employees so that they are not fired. Employees themselves will be allowed to withhold social security payments (Ukrinform, 2020).

The Government of Finland has allocated a total of 15 billion euros to save the Finland economy from the spread of coronavirus. All entrepreneurs, including freelancers, will be entitled to temporary unemployment benefits for three months. The government has provided Business Finland with additional resources of € 150 million for immediate business support measures. These activities are intended for SMEs operating in Finland in the field of tourism (ancillary tourism) services, creative and concert areas and other areas where subcontracting services are received.

Funding is for companies to explore and take advantage of new business opportunities in emergencies. Pension contributions will be deferred for three months. Companies will be able to postpone the payment of taxes for March – May to a later date. And all these measures will be financed by new loans taken by the state. Separately, the government supports the affected aircraft: the national airline Finnair must provide financial assistance in the amount of 600 million euros (Solonyna, 2020).

Figure 1. Financial burden of the Coronavirus Control Fund in the world

3. The Legal Provision of Social Protection of the Population in the Conditions of COVID 19

Following Ukraine's ratification of the Association Agreement with the European Union, it seeks to move closer to European standards. The above examples of the application of social protection measures in the form of material and financial support of all segments of the population affected by the pandemic indicate the indifference of the state to the category of population that provides the economic component of state development, as well as directing almost a third of funds. providing material assistance to vulnerable groups.

Regarding the legal provision of social protection of the population of Ukraine in the conditions of coronavirus disease, it is worth mentioning the following regulations:

- Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts Aimed at Providing Additional Social and Economic Guarantees in Connection with the Spread of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-2019)" No.540 (The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2020c);

- Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Aimed at Preventing the Occurrence and Spread of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19)" 30530 (The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2020b);

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "Some issues of social support for families with children" dated 22.04.2020 No.329 (The Cabinet of Ministers, 2020f);

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "Some issues of state social assistance" from 08.04.2020 No.264 (The Cabinet of Ministers, 2020c);

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "Some issues of restrictive anti-epidemic measures aimed at preventing the spread of acute respiratory disease COVID-19 caused by coronavirus SARS-CoV-2" from 25.03.2020 No.245 (The Cabinet of Ministers, 2020a);

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On the peculiarities of housing subsidies" from 25.03.2020 No.247 (The Cabinet of Ministers, 2020b).

The above-mentioned regulations are aimed at strengthening social protection of the population for the period of taking measures aimed at preventing the occurrence and spread of acute respiratory disease COVID-19. In addition to financial support for particularly vulnerable groups, a number of measures were taken to support business.

A.V. Strizhkova (2020) notes that, from an economic point of view, all the above changes are not possible in full without the proper functioning of economic entities. In the current

context, governments in all countries are working to support businesses. In Ukraine, in particular, a number of urgent measures have been taken to support domestic businesses, including a partial easing of fiscal pressures (through the introduction of tax breaks and exemptions from taxation of supplies of goods necessary to implement pandemic measures, a moratorium for tax audits, etc.). However, given that the scale of business and government losses due to the crisis caused by the pandemic is difficult to fully assess, experts emphasize the need for government support for business for at least the next few years.

O. Kiselyova (2020) identifies the main measures of social protection for the affected business:

- natural persons-entrepreneurs are temporarily exempted from accrual and payment of the single social contribution;
- introduction of a moratorium on inspections of business by regulatory authorities;
- it is prohibited to impose fines for violations of tax legislation;
- introduction of a ban on eviction of tenants for non-payment of utilities and no fines and penalties for non-payment of utilities;
- natural persons-entrepreneurs are exempted from paying fines and - fines for breach of consumer lending agreements;
- employees of small and medium-sized enterprises, for which the employer keeps jobs, can receive partial unemployment benefits;
- deferred payment of mortgage loans;
- legal entities and natural persons-entrepreneurs are exempt from paying land tax.

Recently, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On Additional measures of social support for insured persons for the period of restrictive anti-epidemic measures introduced to prevent the spread of acute respiratory disease COVID-19 caused by coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 in Ukraine" from April 7, 2021 assistance was provided in the amount of 8 thousand "to employees of the business entity or natural persons - entrepreneurs, whose main type of economic activity is indicated first in the information from the Unified State Register of Legal Entities, Individual Entrepreneurs and Public Associations as of the last day of the month preceding the month in which applies for assistance (hereinafter - the application), and corresponds to the types identified in the list of major economic activities in respect of which restrictive anti-epidemic measures are implemented to prevent the spread of certain administrative-territorial units of acute respiratory disease COVID-19, caused by coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, which lead to temporary suspension of business entities in which the insured persons work, and natural persons - entrepreneurs", which was approved by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of December 9, 2020 No. 1236. In addition, this The Resolution stipulates that local self-government bodies may pay at the expense of the local budget assistance to insured persons in the amount determined by them. The procedure for payment of such assistance is determined by local governments (The Cabinet of Ministers, 2020e).

It should be noted that a similar procedure was carried out in the winter of 2020, when it was issued. According to the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 8,000 hryvnias were received by more than 480,000 individuals, entrepreneurs and employees, to whom the state paid more than 3.8 billion hryvnias. Entrepreneurs received another 200 million hryvnias to compensate for the single social contribution. For comparison, according to Opendatabot, there are more than 1.9 million individual entrepreneurs in Ukraine. Thus, if each of the individual entrepreneurs employs at least one worker, it will be a little more than three million. It follows that about 10 percent of individual entrepreneurs and employees received assistance.

Therefore, in general, citizens in both 2020 and 2021 were extremely negative about such social payments of "support" from the state for small businesses. According to experts, such social protection measures are not enough to eliminate the consequences caused by coronavirus

infection. I.M. Wagner (2020) identifies the following possible steps that can improve the financial situation of small and medium-sized businesses after their quarantine:

- first, debts and loans from partners and financial institutions need to be deducted;
- secondly, review the terms of the rent from the property, while making a certain discount, or apply deferral mechanisms;
- thirdly, consider the possibility of conducting the maximum number of employees on the simplified taxation system in order to reduce the tax burden on such entities;
- fourth, consider reducing or sending unpaid staff on temporary unpaid leave, while ensuring that critical company personnel are protected during the crisis;
- fifth, instead of downsizing, if possible, staff can be transferred to other types of work (for example, developing new services and products that were in demand during the crisis, or planning and preparing for the resumption of the company after the crisis) or even temporarily lend to other companies, even at a discount;
- sixth, consider the possibility of limiting the hiring of new staff, because it is possible that in the near future market wages for certain professions will decline, and therefore in the labor market - there will be many free professionals;
- seventh definition of mechanisms for calculating the cost of work for consultants who provide services to find a new business model and not close in difficult times;
- eighth, the organization of support measures for businesses that have gone online (such as direct assistance or benefits);
- and the last - public procurement to support small and medium-sized businesses.

A. Bobrova and L. Lomonosova (2020) offer short-term measures aimed at overcoming the consequences of the pandemic and quarantine, and long-term measures aimed at reforming social protection policy. Among the key they highlight:

- opening of new staff units in the relevant public institutions (tercentres, social centers);
- in cities and villages where there is a lack of funding from the budgets of the district, city or OTG, the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine should provide adequate funding for territorial centers, as well as other state and municipal institutions in charge of social services;
- to create necessary and favorable conditions for the purpose of safe visiting of social or territorial centers for those people who need services on social adaptation, rehabilitation, day care;
- in a special way to provide social protection workers with a decent salary, with the obligatory improvement of their working conditions.

4. Conclusion

Thus, having conducted a detailed analysis of social protection in a pandemic from a legal and economic point of view, it is worth mentioning the following key positions. Social protection of the population - is a kind of state support of certain or defined by the legislation of Ukraine categories of the population that are particularly vulnerable to economic processes taking place in Ukraine, which aims to ensure a decent standard of living by providing material, legal or financial assistance to such segments. also the creation of social guarantees for the economically secure (ie for the active) category of the population, while creating acceptable conditions for the country, conditions for life and work of citizens, including through the establishment of social standards.

Based on the proposed author's definition, it was found that social protection always applies to two categories of the population: economically active and economically passive citizens. Emphasis is placed on the fact that in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the State's attention should be focused not only on particularly vulnerable (economically passive) citizens, but also on the economically active population, which has suffered serious financial losses and reduced staffing, reducing the number of turnover. It was found that since the

beginning of 2020, the normative-legal provision of social protection of the population in the conditions of a pandemic has numbered more than fifty normative-legal acts concerning two categories of the population. In particular, such social protection measures concern: availability of additional financial support; introduction of grace periods for the economically active population; compensation for housing and communal services, etc.

It is determined that the member states of the European Union have many times more financial support from the Coronavirus Control Funds. Of course, this can be explained by the greater economic development of such states, when even in a pandemic it allows them to occupy leading positions in the world economic market. There is also a need to take into account international experience in terms of special support for large and medium-sized businesses.

Thus, in a COVID-19 pandemic it is necessary to:

- strengthen the targeting of housing subsidies to the population;
- to introduce payments from material assistance for children for the period of quarantine and for one month after the date of its cancellation on natural persons-entrepreneurs, who are on the third group of single taxpayers;
- to provide targeted adequate financial assistance to women who lost their jobs during quarantine;
- to provide financial support to women who are raising minor children without person, as well as those who lost their jobs during the pandemic;
- strengthen the targeting of state social support to the most vulnerable segments of the population and ensure control over its provision;
- use the funds of the Coronavirus Fund only for its intended purpose.

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